

Simulation-based Control of Tool Wear and Lifetime for Titanium Machining

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Abstract

The prediction of tool life time in machining processes has been subject to research since the beginning of machining technology itself. Already in the early 1900s Taylor [1] found a basic correlation between tool life time and cutting velocity in turning. The Taylor equation has later been improved by also taking the chip thickness into account. However, not the equation is the problem in computing the tool life time but the parametrization for a certain pair of tool and work material. Especially for the machining of titanium alloys with sharp tools where the tool wear mainly consists of smaller or greater splintering of the cutting edges it is hard to determine the state of a somehow worn cutting edge as a scalar value. This makes it hard to measure the progression of the tool wear from a new tool towards a finally worn one. Especially the point in time at which the final wear, i. e. the end of the tool life, is reached is hard to determine. Another problem that is related to tool wear is the effect on the cutting forces. As far as it is not possible to simulate the tool wear progression it does not make sense to try to predict the point in time where the end of tool life is reached. Measurements of the spindle torque with differently worn tools have shown that a simple extension of the Kienzle equation enables the inclusion of the tool wear into the cutting force computation. Vice versa, when the undeformed chip form is known it is possible to recompute the current wear state from the spindle torque. This enables the measurement of both the tool wear progression and the end of tool life and therefore to develop a tool wear model that is taking the undeformed chip form into account. This allows the computation of the tool wear progression even along any NC-program with continuously changing undeformed chip forms.

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1 Introduction

The modelling of tool wear along an NC-program can save production costs by reducing the probability of tool breakage and by enabling the usage of tools for as long as possible. So far, an automatic tool change is executed when the tool has expended its specific constant life time in G1-mode regardless of what kind of operation the tool has performed during that time period. Therefore, tools may be worn out before the tool change if they have encountered adverse conditions or they may still be in good shape otherwise.

By simulating tool wear, it is possible to compute the feed rate in a way that ensures the desired life time on the one hand, and on the other hand, to shift the point in time when the automatic tool change will occur. For this, a wear model has been developed that is based on a scalar value (i. e. the wear state r_c) that can be measured by the spindle torque or the cutting force, respectively.

Recently, the modelling of tool wear has been mainly related to FEM-simulations [2,3] which are applicable for technological investigations but not for the industrial usage in serial production. Other approaches like [4] apply wear models on a machining simulation which use discrete workpiece models like dixel boards to obtain the uncut chip shape, which is then correlated to the tool life-time. Thereby, the tool life-time is measured

conventionally. Dxel models need a high resolution in order to render even small undeformed chips. Therefore, this approach is not applicable to aircraft frames of sizes up to a length of six meters.

2 Constant Offset in Spindle Torque and Kienzle Equation

It has been found that especially sharp tungsten carbide tools – as used at Premium AEROTEC – in first approximation apply a constant offset to the spindle torque rather than a factor when they are worn. This implies that there must also be a constant offset to the cutting force model (e. g. the Kienzle equation). This offset – called r_c – has the unit N/mm like a specific cutting force. Therefore, it is an additional force per mm of the cutting edge that is additionally produced by the current tool wear. When performing cutting tests with constant cutting parameters (axial immersion a_p , radial immersion a_e , cutting velocity v_c , and feed per tooth f_z) and measuring the spindle torque (e. g. by reading the related variable from the NC-controller or using a process monitoring system) the value r_c can be recomputed using a milling simulation by adjusting r_c in a way that the simulated spindle torque equals the measured one. By comparing r_c to the visual appearance of the cutting edge the additional specific cutting force at the end of tool life was determined as 40 N/mm. This is the point where the cutting edges appear strongly damaged but can still be reground.

With this, we have a scalar value r_c that describes the wear state of the cutting edge for the first time. Herewith, it is possible to perform cutting tests in order to parametrize and enhance a wear model like the enhanced Taylor equation [1].

3 Wear Model

The wear model, at first specific for a tungsten carbide tool of diameter 25 mm (Figure 1), mainly consists of the enhanced Taylor equation with an additional extension to account for the entry chip thickness [4]. First, we compute a value e_s called *life time equivalent* e_s :

$$e_s(a_e, v_c, f_z) = a_e^a \cdot v_c^b \cdot f_z^c - d \cdot h_e.$$

Hereby, h_e is the entry chip thickness which is the uncut chip thickness at the point in time where the cutting edge enters the material at the beginning of each cut. The parameters a , b , c , and d were calibrated by milling tests so that e_s was approximately equal for different parameters when the related tool life time was equal. It turned out that the tool life time itself is not generally linear in e_s .

Figure 1 shows the results of milling tests with varying milling parameters. With $a = 0.674$, $b = 1.497$, $c = 0.016$, and $d = 0.016$ the results best fit to a square function. This square function applied to the tool life equivalent e_s is the final model to determine the tool life time.

Figure 1: Results of tool life measurements (left) for the tungsten carbide tool with diameter 25 mm (right).

4 Control of Tool Wear and Life

With the tool life-time model the milling simulation can now compute the milling parameters along the NC-program in constant time steps (by a non-discrete approach for modelling the uncut chip form [6]) and compute whether the wear rate is within the desired window, too low or too high. In case of excessive tool wear, the feed rate can be reduced in order to achieve the desired life-time. In case of too low wear the feed rate can be increased if it is not limited by any other parameter like maximal force or chip thickness. Another possibility

is to manipulate the elapsed time in G1 mode that is stored in an NC-controller-variable in order to achieve a longer usage of the tool. In this way the tool wear can be controlled in order to maximize productivity.

5 Conclusion

With the wear state r_c defined as an *additional* specific cutting force it is possible to describe the current tool wear state as a scalar value instead of the commonly used measurement of the width and depth of wear marks. By measuring the spindle torque while conducting wear experiments one can recompute the current wear state r_c , which leads to detailed data of the wear progression. It is no more necessary to perform microscopic measurements after each machined line of the tool path. This detailed data was the base for the development of a tool wear model which can also be applied on arbitrary NC-programs in order to optimize the usage of tungsten carbide tools.

Since the tool wear is modelled as an additional specific cutting force, it can be directly fed back into the cutting force model in order to compute the increase of the cutting forces along the tool path. This also enables the prediction of the point where the tool may be overloaded absolutely.

Future work will focus on the application of the same method on inserted tools on the one hand and on the machining of steel on the other hand.

6 References

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